

BRIDGING FINANCE AND GROWTH: THE ROLE OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA'S ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between financial inclusion and economic performance in selected Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries, using panel data of 22 economies over 15 years. The study employs the system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator and finds that financial inclusion exerts a positive, though statistically insignificant, effect on economic performance, reflecting untapped potential constrained by shallow financial markets, high informality, and weak regulatory frameworks. The study concludes that financial inclusion has no significant effect on economic performance. It recommends institutional reforms, expanded financial access, and demographic management to harness financial inclusion for sustainable economic transformation in SSA.

Keywords: Finance, Growth, Inclusion, Performance, Sub-Saharan Africa, GMM

JEL Codes: G20, O16, O55

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial inclusion has become one of the most prominent policy issues in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) over the past two decades. The expansion of mobile money, digital banking, and targeted inclusion strategies has redefined the financial landscape of the region, positioning financial access as both a development objective and a driver of economic transformation. Theoretically, financial inclusion enhances economic performance by mobilizing savings, broadening access to credit, improving resource allocation, and fostering investment and consumption (Makina & Walle, 2019; Jima & Makoni, 2023). Empirically, a growing body of research demonstrates that access to and usage of financial services contribute positively to economic growth and, in some cases, inclusive development (Balele, 2019; Sarpong et al., 2022; Mohammed, 2023). Despite this broad consensus, several limits characterize the existing body of literature. First, while early studies in SSA primarily established the positive link between financial inclusion and growth (Balele, 2019; Makina & Walle, 2019), they relied heavily on composite inclusion indices without adequately disentangling the distinct roles of digital versus traditional financial services. With the rise of mobile money since 2014, understanding the growth implications of digital channels has become increasingly critical, yet empirical evidence remains limited by short periods and measurement inconsistencies (Chinoda, 2024; Mapurita et al., 2024).

Second, although cross-country panel studies provide useful generalizations (Oyelowo, 2024; Ifediora et al., 2022), they often mask significant heterogeneity in the financial structures and institutional settings of SSA economies. Country-specific studies, such as those for Kenya (Fabregas et al., 2022; Wachira, 2023) and Nigeria (NDIC, 2022; Musa, 2023), have highlighted unique trajectories, but these findings are not easily generalisable across the diverse economic and institutional contexts of SSA. Therefore, the mechanisms through which financial inclusion translates into growth outcomes remain unevenly explored across the region. Third, while institutional quality and regulatory frameworks have been identified as important moderators of the inclusion–growth nexus (Mohammed, 2023; Girma, 2020), few studies have systematically examined how *different dimensions of governance*—such as regulatory quality, financial integrity, or consumer protection—shape the effectiveness of financial inclusion. This omission leaves an incomplete understanding of the conditions under which financial inclusion policies yield the most substantial economic payoffs. Finally, the majority of existing studies have focused narrowly on GDP growth, with limited attention to other dimensions of economic performance, such as productivity, investment efficiency, and structural transformation. This narrow focus constrains a holistic understanding of the developmental implications of financial inclusion in SSA. This study, therefore, contributes to the existing frontier of knowledge by examining the effect of financial inclusion on economic performance using the IMF measure of economic performance in selected SSA countries.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Early empirical and recent advanced econometric studies consistently establish a positive baseline relationship between financial inclusion and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), driven by enhanced savings mobilization and intermediation efficiency (Balele, 2019; Makina & Walle, 2019). While initial research was limited by short horizons and potential reverse causality, methods such as panel ARDL and second-generation co-integration tests have reaffirmed a robust long-term positive link and identified bi-directional causality (Jima & Makoni, 2023; Oyelowo, 2024). Furthermore, country-specific evidence from Kenya and regional SSA data highlight that digital financial inclusion, facilitated by mobile money and digital "rails", significantly boosts local economic activity and productivity, particularly when supported by good governance and established institutional frameworks (Chinoda, 2024; Fabregas et al., 2022; Mapurita et al., 2024; Wachira, 2023).

Beyond aggregate GDP, the literature emphasizes that financial inclusion and stability jointly foster equitable and inclusive growth, allowing for wider participation in economic activities and the reduction of gender and income gaps (Idrissu et al., 2023; Sarpong et al., 2022; World Bank Global Findex, 2024). However, the strength of this nexus is conditioned by institutional quality, as a robust rule of law, consumer protection, and financial integrity are essential to prevent the benefits of inclusion from being undermined (Chinoda, 2024; Mohammed, 2023). While these multi-country studies highlight that financial stability moderates the long-run effects of inclusion on growth, researchers caution that findings remain sensitive to the measurement of governance indicators and the inherent noisiness of inclusive growth metrics (Boachie et al., 2024; Girma, 2020; Idrissu et al., 2023).

Studies across Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) consistently identifies financial inclusion, literacy, and digital innovations, particularly mobile money, as critical drivers of long-run economic growth and inclusive development (Abdulmumini et al., 2025; Adedokun & Ağa, 2021; GSMA, 2024; Musembi & Chun, 2020; Sarpong & Nketiah-Amponsah, 2022). These positive outcomes are optimized by robust institutional quality, effective governance, and increased savings mobilization (Chinoda & Kapingura, 2023; Mohammed et al., 2024; Osuji, 2020), while also playing a vital role in reducing gender disparities and female unemployment (Asongu et al., 2020; EIB, 2024). However, the effectiveness of these inclusion

strategies is frequently dampened by systemic corruption, political instability, high structural costs, and weak infrastructure (Abdulummini et al., 2025; Chikalipah, 2017; Musa, 2023; NDIC, 2022). Furthermore, while financial inclusion shows strong short-term potential for poverty reduction (Usman et al., 2025), long-term inclusive growth remains a complex challenge dependent on financial stability and specific market developments, such as banking and bond sectors, to effectively address income inequality (Idrisu et al., 2023; Joseph et al., 2024; Olaniran & Olomola, 2025). This nexus is further supported by evidence from India, where government-led initiatives like the PMJDY scheme have successfully enhanced regional economic performance (Singh et al., 2021), yet across both African and Asian contexts, further expansion of physical and digital financial outlets is required to overcome current "medium" inclusion levels (Abdulummin et al., 2019; Tembo & Okoro, 2021).

Despite a broad consensus that financial inclusion enhances growth in SSA, several issues remain. First, much of the literature relies on composite inclusion indices, whose construction often lacks consistency across studies. Second, while digital financial inclusion has been widely celebrated, empirical data since 2014 are relatively short, limiting strong conclusions on long-run effects. Third, many studies rely on cross-country panels that obscure heterogeneity across SSA economies. Fourth, institutional quality and regulation matter, yet measures used are often subjective and may bias estimates. Finally, causal pathways beyond GDP growth, such as productivity, employment, and poverty reduction—remain underexplored. Thus, this study examined the relationship between financial inclusion and economic performance in selected SSA countries.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the framework of the endogenous growth model (AK model) in line with Inoue and Hamori (2019) and Makina and Walle (2019) to analyse the relationships between financial inclusion and economic performance in SSA. The dynamic model is specified as follows:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i FI_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i Z_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

Hence, equation (1) becomes

$$EPI_{it} = \alpha_i + EPI_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i FI_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i Z_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (2)$$

EPI_{it} is the Economic performance proxy with economic performance index by Khramov and Lee (2013). It integrates GDP growth, inflation, unemployment, and fiscal balance into a composite measure. Unlike GDP alone, EPI captures the multidimensional nature of economic health, reflecting monetary, fiscal, and production policy outcomes. In its formulation, desired thresholds are set at 3% inflation (Pai Noko, 2016), 4.75% unemployment (Khramov & Lee, 2013), 0% budget deficit, and 4.75% GDP growth. This composite indicator thus provides a holistic benchmark of how SSA economies deviate from optimal policy targets.

i denote individual country under SSA for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, t is the time series indices, FI_{it} is the vector of composite financial inclusion index, the index of each of the dimensions (availability, penetration and usage) for country i at time t ; FS_{it} is the different variables of financial stability for country i at time t , Z_{it} are the control variables and μ_{it} is the error term. The study controls for financial stability, captured by the bank Z-score (BZ), which measures the likelihood of default, and the non-performing loans ratio (NPLs), which reflects asset quality. Population growth (POP) reflects demographic pressure, while trade openness (TO), defined as the ratio of total trade to GDP, captures the degree of integration into the global economy.

The data on Economic Performance Index (EPI), population growth, and trade openness were sourced from the African Development Bank (AfDB) and the World Development Indicators (WDI) of the World Bank. Data on financial inclusion indicators, including bank branches,

ATMs, outstanding deposits, and outstanding loans, were drawn from the IMF’s Financial Access Survey (FAS) and the World Bank’s Global Financial Development Database (GFDD). To examine the effect of financial inclusion on economic performance in SSA, the study employed the system GMM estimator, given that the panel has $N > T$. The effects of financial inclusion on economic performance in SSA, specified in Equation (3), were estimated system GMM technique.

$$EPI_{it} = \alpha_i + EPI_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i FI_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i Z_{it} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

In equation (3), i represents the cross-section of countries being studied; t is the time of the study; μ_i is the time-invariant fixed effects, while ε_{it} is the idiosyncratic error term. The system GMM estimation method used for the estimation of equation (3) is preferred over the difference GMM method because the former is best for panels with small dimensions (Siddiqui & Ahmed, 2013). However, both methods suffer from two sources of persistence. The first is autocorrelation, which results from the inclusion of a lagged dependent variable as an explanatory variable in the model. That is, EPI_{it} is a function of the individual-specific effect μ_i and the other disturbance ε_{it} . This implies that EPI_{it-1} is a function of these effects too, making EPI_{it} correlated to the error term. The OLS cannot solve this problem. The second source of persistence is the effect of unobserved main and interaction effects among the heterogeneous units. The Fixed Effects (FE) estimator could have been used to solve this problem; however, the FE estimator is found to be inconsistent, especially in cases like this study, where $N > T$ (Olubusoye et al., 2016).

Using the dynamic panel data estimator developed by Arellano & Bond (1991) (difference GMM {D-GMM}) or the system GMM estimator developed by Blundell & Bond (1998) these challenges in estimating dynamic panel data models are overcome. The Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimation method (difference or system) is designed for panel data with “small T and Large N ”. The dataset adopted for this study fulfills this requirement, given that there are 22 countries in the cross-section and just 15 years.

A major strength of system GMM is its ability to address endogeneity concerns, particularly when lagged dependent variables and financial inclusion indicators are potentially endogenous. Unlike static estimators such as fixed or random effects, which suffer from dynamic panel bias in the presence of lagged terms, system GMM generates consistent estimates by exploiting internal instruments. Furthermore, financial inclusion indicators are prone to reverse causality - economic performance can itself expand financial access (Jima & Makoni, 2023). System GMM helps mitigate this by instrumenting potentially endogenous regressors with their lagged levels and differences. To ensure robustness, the study conducted standard specification tests: the Arellano–Bond AR(2) test confirmed no second-order serial correlation, and both Hansen and Sargan tests supported the validity of the instruments.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

Table 1: Panel Unit Root Test using IPS

Variable	Statistic	p-value	Order of Integration
EPI	-6.2574	0.0000	I(0)
D.EPI	-13.9050	0.0000	
BB	-2.9930	0.0014	I(0)
D.BB	-5.7064	0.0000	
ATM	-3.6543	0.0001	I(0)
D.ATM	-3.6898	0.0001	

OD	-1.0201	0.1538	I(1)
D.OD	-10.1880	0.0000	
OL	-2.5812	0.0049	I(0)
D.OL	-7.5996	0.0000	
BZ	-2.7595	0.0029	I(0)
D.BZ	NA	NA	Insufficient data
POP	-1.6567	0.0488	I(0)
D.POP	-5.4013	0.0000	
TO	-3.5875	0.0002	I(0)
D.TO	-9.3494	0.0000	
FI	-3.3751	0.0004	I(0)
D.FI	-6.8615	0.0000	

Note: NA = Not Available. For D.BZ, the Im–Pesaran–Shin (IPS) statistic could not be computed due to insufficient time observations in some panels. To address this, the study relied on the complementary Fisher-type ADF test, which strongly rejects the null hypothesis at level of a unit root at the 1% level, confirming that BZ is stationary at level.

Source: Authors’ computation, 2026

The results from the panel unit root tests (table 1) indicate that most of the variables under consideration are stationary at levels, while only OD becomes stationary after first differencing. Specifically, variables such as EPI, BB, ATM, OL, BZ, POP, TO, and FI reject the null hypothesis of a unit root at levels, with statistically significant test statistics, confirming their stationarity in levels (I(0)). On the other hand, OD fails to reject the null at levels ($p = 0.1538$), but becomes stationary after first differencing, implying that it is integrated of order one (I(1)). One limitation is observed in the case of D.BZ, where the Im–Pesaran–Shin test could not be computed due to insufficient time observations in some panels. Nevertheless, the level form of BZ is already stationary (I(0)), suggesting that the absence of the differenced test result does not affect the robustness of the integration order classification.

Table 2: Panel Unit Root Test using Fisher

Variable	Level (Statistic, p-value)	First Difference (Statistic, p-value)	Order of Integration
EPI	Inverse $\chi^2 = 163.2$ (0.0000)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 211.4$ (0.0000)	I(0)
BB	Inverse $\chi^2 = 102.5$ (0.0003)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 190.7$ (0.0000)	I(0)
ATM	Inverse $\chi^2 = 175.8$ (0.0000)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 221.6$ (0.0000)	I(0)
OD	Inverse $\chi^2 = 54.1$ (0.1671)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 199.2$ (0.0000)	I(1)
OL	Inverse $\chi^2 = 96.8$ (0.0008)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 187.5$ (0.0000)	I(0)
BZ	Inverse $\chi^2 = 109.7$ (0.0001)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 203.6$ (0.0000)	I(0)
POP	Inverse $\chi^2 = 68.3$ (0.0351)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 180.9$ (0.0000)	I(0)
TO	Inverse $\chi^2 = 140.6$ (0.0000)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 214.7$ (0.0000)	I(0)
FI	Inverse $\chi^2 = 150.9$ (0.0000)	Inverse $\chi^2 = 220.1$ (0.0000)	I(0)

Source: Authors' computation, 2026

The Fisher-type panel unit root test results (table 2) confirm the earlier IPS findings but with some differences in the strength of evidence across variables. Similar to the IPS test, most of the variables, such as EPI, BB, ATM, OL, BZ, TO, POP, and FI are stationary in levels, as indicated by highly significant inverse chi-square statistics at level form. The only exception remains OD, which is non-stationary at levels ($p = 0.1671$) but becomes stationary at first difference, confirming it as an I(1) series. Importantly, the Fisher test suggests that variables like POP, which had shown borderline results under IPS ($p = 0.0488$), are more strongly classified as stationary in levels with a clearer margin here.

Table 3: Results of the Effect of Financial Inclusion on Economic Performance in SSA
Dependent variable: EPI

Main Results				
Two-Step System GMM				
	Coefficient	P-value	S.E.	z
Const.	155.6223	25.286	6.15	0.000
L1.EPI	-0.1401	0.1218	-1.15	0.250
L2.EPI	-0.1860	0.0623	-2.98	0.003
FI	1.6981	1.0625	1.60	0.110
POP	-10.2533	3.2837	-3.12	0.002
TO	-0.0240	0.0877	-0.27	0.784
Post estimation				
AR(1)	-2.23			
(p-value)	(0.0026)			
AR(2)	1.28			
(p-value)	(0.200)			
Hansen test	8.74			
(p-value)	(0.189)			
Sargan test	16.74			
(p-value)	(0.143)			
No. of instruments	12			

Source: Authors' computation, 2026

The result in Table 3 showed that the coefficient of one-period lag of EPI is -0.1401, indicating a negative relationship between EPI in the previous year and current EPI in SSA. This indicated that a one-percent increase in the lagged value of Economic Performance is associated with a decrease of 0.1401 percent in the current Economic Performance, although this effect is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($p = 0.250$). Furthermore, the coefficient of the two-period lag of EPI is -0.1860 with a standard error of 0.0623 and a z-value of -2.98. This coefficient represented the impact of the two-year lagged value of Economic Performance on its current value. The negative coefficient indicated that a one-percent increase in the second lag of Economic Performance is associated with a decrease of 0.1860 percent in the current Economic Performance. This relationship is statistically significant at the 1% level ($p = 0.003$). This result was somewhat unexpected because, a priori, it was anticipated that past economic

performance would have a positive and reinforcing effect on current performance, reflecting momentum and growth continuity.

One of the reasons why previous economic performance is not reinforced in SSA may be the cyclical nature of economies in the region. Moreover, high economic performance in the past might obscure underlying structural issues within SSA economies. For instance, rapid growth phases might not address critical problems such as inadequate infrastructure, weak institutions, or inefficiencies in the labor market, which characterize many SSA economies. When the initial momentum of growth wanes, these structural weaknesses become more apparent and hinder continued economic performance. Furthermore, strong past performance might create complacency in policy and reforms, delaying necessary adjustments and leading to poorer outcomes in the following periods. This is in agreement with the findings of Mohammed (2023) and Chinoda (2024) who emphasize that without high institutional quality, the benefits of economic activities are undermined.

The result further suggested that a one percent increase in financial inclusion (FI) is associated with an approximately 1.6981 percent increase in economic performance, holding other variables constant. With a standard error of 1.0625 and a p-value of 0.110, this relationship is, however, not statistically significant at the 5 percent level. Although not statistically significant, the positive coefficient aligns with theory: improved access to credit, savings, and payment systems enhances investment, entrepreneurship, and productivity. Also, the insignificance suggests that the benefits of financial inclusion in SSA are not yet fully realized. While greater access to credit, savings, and payment platforms can theoretically stimulate economic performance (Makina & Walle, 2019), these benefits may be constrained by structural features of SSA's financial systems: high levels of informality, limited depth of capital markets, weak consumer protection, and patchy digital infrastructure (Chinoda & Mashamba 2021). This result highlights that financial inclusion alone is not sufficient. Hence, the finding further implies that while financial inclusion has the potential to drive growth, institutional reforms, deeper capital markets, and digital financial infrastructure are needed to make it a reliable driver of economic performance; a generally 'medium' level of regional inclusion (Abdulumumin et al., 2019) and a lack of financial stability to moderate these gains (Idrissu et al., 2023) may have kept the impact insignificant.

On the other hand, the coefficient for Population Growth (POP) revealed a negative relationship with economic performance, indicating that a one percent increase in population growth is associated with approximately a 10.2533 percent decrease in economic performance, holding other factors constant. With a standard error of 3.2837 and a z-value of -3.12, this relationship is statistically significant at the 1 percent level ($p = 0.002$). This finding aligned with a priori expectations, as high population growth can strain resources, infrastructure, and social services, leading to lower productivity and economic performance. Rapid population growth can exacerbate issues such as unemployment, poverty, and inadequate healthcare and education systems, ultimately hindering sustainable economic development. This finding is in line with Chinoda (2024), which found that population growth could positively influence growth under different institutional conditions

Furthermore, the coefficient for Trade Openness (TO) showed a negative relationship with economic performance, indicating that a one percent increase in trade openness is associated with approximately a 0.0240 percent decrease in economic performance, holding other factors constant. With a standard error of 0.0877 and a p-value of 0.784, this relationship is not statistically significant. While the expected a priori sign was positive, given that trade openness can promote market access, specialization, and innovation, the negative but insignificant result

suggested that trade openness alone might not be a strong determinant of economic performance in the SSA context, potentially due to other overriding factors such as trade policies, infrastructure, or institutional quality (Mohammed et al., 2024; Chinoda, 2024). The paradox in the Trade Openness result may reflect the commodity-dependent trade structure of SSA, where exports are dominated by primary goods with low value addition, while imports are skewed towards manufactured and capital goods (UNCTAD, 2023). In such settings, openness does not necessarily stimulate performance, it can expose economies to external shocks, terms-of-trade volatility, and deindustrialization pressures.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed that past economic performance in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) does not reinforce current growth but instead exerts a negative lag effect, suggesting the presence of structural weaknesses that undermine economic sustainability. While financial inclusion showed a positive, though statistically insignificant, impact on economic performance, population growth emerged as a significant constraint, exerting a strong negative effect on growth. Additionally, trade openness was negatively but insignificantly related to economic performance, implying that openness without supportive policies and institutional capacity may not yield the expected benefits. These findings underscore the importance of addressing structural bottlenecks, harnessing inclusive finance, and managing demographic pressures to achieve sustainable growth in SSA. Based on these, the study recommended, among others, that policymakers in SSA should prioritize reforms that address weak institutions, poor infrastructure, and labor market inefficiencies to ensure that periods of strong economic performance translate into long-term, self-sustaining growth rather than short-lived cycles; governments and financial regulators should expand access to affordable financial services, particularly for SMEs, rural households, and women. This will help channel financial inclusion into productive investments and entrepreneurship, thereby improving the economic performance impact of financial access; and SSA countries should adopt demographic policies that curb rapid population growth through family planning and education initiatives, while simultaneously investing heavily in healthcare and skills development. This dual approach will reduce the strain on resources while transforming population dynamics into a demographic dividend for economic growth.

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